

**NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF
TRADITIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL ZINC-BASED COATINGS: PART II**

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ABSTRACT (200 words)

In the present paper, the bending behaviour of hot-dip galvanising hot-rolled hyper-sandelin plates, together with the corresponding crack pattern, are numerically investigated by using a hybrid model developed in Ansys LS-DYNA environment, by combining the Discrete Element Method (DEM) with Finite Element Method (FEM). The experimental bending tests here simulated and available in the literature were performed by considering two types of bath that is: a pure zinc bath and a technological bath, consisting in a zinc bath with 3% Sn addition by weight. The results related to the bending

behaviour are compared with both experimental data and other FE numerical results, previously obtained by some of the present authors. Moreover, the numerical crack patterns are compared with the experimental observations of the longitudinal section of the plates at the end of testing, by means of a light optical microscope. A quite satisfactory agreement is observed.

KEYWORDS

Damage; Finite Element Method; Lattice Discrete Element Method; technological coating; zinc-based coatings

1. INTRODUCTION

Steel remains one of the most used materials for both construction of automobiles and industrial machineries and civil constructions due to its high strength and durability. However, the action of different environmental agents on steel can lead to a corrosion process. Among the methods employed to prevent steel corrosion, there is the hot-dip galvanising (HDG), a process of coating offering increased corrosion resistance of steel at moderate costs [1]. The so-called galvanized steels are produced by a process where steel parts are hot-dipped in a bath of molten zinc for a given time interval and at a predefined temperature. The zinc coating protects steel by means of a cathodic reaction, corroding itself instead of steel, due to the different electromechanical potential of these two materials (active protection) [2].

When the steel is dipped in the zinc bath (the industrial standard temperature is equal to 450 °C), a series of zinc-iron alloy layers (intermetallic phases) are formed (**Figure 1**), consisting in: gamma (Γ - 75%Zn;25%Fe by weight), delta (δ - 90%Zn;10%Fe by weight), zeta (ζ - 94%Zn;6%Fe by weight), and eta (η - 100%Zn) [1,3,4]. Such intermetallic phases differ from one another for microstructure, mechanical and thermal properties [5], being such properties influenced by many factors such as, for example, bath composition, dipping time and bath temperature [6-8].

The intermetallic phases can exhibit multiple cracks under both thermally induced residual stresses and externally applied stresses [9-11]. As a matter of fact, such loads, generating large

deformations, induce the formation of cracks in the coating. The passage of both air and moisture from the environment through the cracks leads to oxidation and corrosion reactions in both substrate (steel) and coating [12]. Since such cracks affect the lifetime of coated components, thorough understanding of the crack formation process in these layers is essential for advancement of HDG technology.

Figure 1. Intermetallic phases present in a typical hot-dip galvanized coating.

Many experimental investigations have been performed to analyse damage evolution in coated components [11,13-17].

In the experimental studies reported in Refs [13], [15] and [16], performed on galvanized steels under different static loading conditions, it was observed that the brittleness of δ phase (highlighted by the highest microhardness and stiffness and the lowest toughness) with respect to that of ζ and η phases is the main factor that causes damage initiation in coatings. Reumont et al. [15] also highlighted the presence of a relevant crack pattern

formed after the galvanizing process, as a result of the difference between the linear thermal expansion coefficients of the steel with respect to those of intermetallic layers. More precisely, cracks nucleated in the δ phase, and propagated in a direction normal to the coating interface, extending to the ζ phase. Delamination into the ζ layer and at the interface between δ phase and steel substrate was also observed.

Di Cocco et al. [17] analysed the influence of the damage micro-mechanisms in galvanized steel plates under bending loading employing different alloy elements added to a pure-zinc bath (such as Cu, Pb, Sn and Ti). Radial cracks were observed in different positions into the samples: generally the initiation was at steel-coating interface, whereas the arrest was observed either at δ - ζ interface, in ζ phase or at ζ - η interface. In all the investigated bending samples no cracks were present in η phase.

In addition to experimental testing, numerical simulations can help researchers to investigate damage evolution in galvanized steel under different loading conditions.

In the work by Song et al. [18] a two-grain model, that exploited the Finite Element Method (FEM), was proposed to assess the fracture behaviour of galvanized coatings. In the works of Parisot et al. [19, 20] analytical and Finite Element models were used to analyse fracture in alloyed zinc coating at the crystallographic level.

It is worth noting that, FEM is one of the most common tool used for the numerical simulation of engineering problems

characterized by both complex geometries and non-linearities involved. In the context of galvanized coatings simulations, FEM was employed by Ploypech et al. [21], Pruncu et al. [22], Carpinteri et al. [23], and Vantadori et al. [24]. Being FEM based on a continuum mechanics approach, it is well known that it has the limitation related to transition between continuum and discontinuum, that is, it is not able to simulate both the initiation and propagation of cracks. Some alternatives to avoid this limitation have been developed, and among them the extended finite element method (XFEM) [25,26] and the cohesive zone model (CZM) [27] used, for example, by Ploypech et al. [12] and Rehman et al. [28], respectively, to analysed the failure of a coating on a ductile substrate.

As an alternative to FEM, the discrete approaches, such as the Discrete Element Methods (DEMs) can be used. The common aspect of such methods is that the mass of the body is discretized by elements, interacting each others according to a given contact or cohesive law. Such an interaction, formulated at the microscopic level, governs the behaviour of the material at the macroscale [29]. Therefore, initially the damage process begins at the microscale, when the interaction between adjacent elements is interrupted for the reaching of a critical value of displacement, strain or energy in the element. Then, when more and more interactions are interrupted, a crack at the macroscale is formed. Among the different versions of the DEM available in the literature, it is worth mentioning those where the continuum is modelled by an assembly of discrete one-dimensional elements such as truss bars [30] and beams

[31]. These models have the ability to consider material disorder, heterogeneities and multi-phase materials, which makes them attractive for meso- or micro-scale simulations of failure phenomena in heterogeneous materials [32].

In the present paper a version of DEM, named Lattice Discrete Element Method (LDEM) and originally proposed by Riera [33] is employed. More precisely, according to the LDEM, a set of masses are joined by uniaxial elements (bars), where the masses are organized in a regular cubic arrangement. Moreover, the bars are characterized by a bilinear constitutive law, based on the Hillerborg model [34], allowing to simulate the breaking of the element itself, and thus taking into account the material damaging. The satisfactory correlation between the experimental results and the LDEM estimations confirms the robustness of such a method, as it was proved in the context of: fracture problems [35,36], analysis of size effect in quasi-brittle materials [37-39], and acoustic emission phenomena in heterogeneous materials [40-43].

In the present paper, the global bending behaviour of HDG hot-rolled hyper-sandelin plates, together with the corresponding crack pattern, is numerically investigated by using a hybrid model developed by employing Ansys LS-DYNA finite element code [44] in conjunction with the LDEM [33]. More precisely, the δ and the ζ layers under tension are modelled by using discrete elements, allowing to capture the nucleation and stable propagation of cracks, whereas the rest of the body is modelled by using finite elements.

The experimental bending tests here examined and available in the literature [17,23,45,46], were performed by considering two types of bath that is: a pure zinc bath and a technological bath, consisting in a zinc bath with 3% Sn addition by weight. For each of the aforementioned baths, five different dipping time values were considered. The numerical results, obtained by the numerical hybrid models developed, and related to the global bending behaviour of coated plates, are compared with both experimental data [17,23,45,46] and other previous numerical results obtained by some of the present authors [24]. Moreover, the numerical crack patterns are compared with the experimental observations of the longitudinal section of the plates at the end of testing, by means of a light optical microscope [17,23,45,46].

The paper is organised as follows. The basic concepts of the LDEM, and its implementation in the Ansys LS-DYNA environment, are presented in **Section 2**. **Section 3** is dedicated to the experimental campaign description here simulated, in terms of specimens, baths composition, dipping times, and testing machine used. **Section 4** is aimed to the numerical models description. Numerical results are presented in **Section 5** and compared with the experimental and the numerical ones available in the literature. Conclusions are summarised in **Section 6**.

2. LATTICE DISCRETE ELEMENT METHOD (LDEM)

The basic formulation of the Lattice Discrete Element Method (LDEM) used in the present work has been presented in other research papers

as, for example, in Refs [39,40,42]. Thus, only a brief description of the method is here presented.

2.1 Basic concepts

The LDEM consists in the discretization of the continuum like a 3D-array of nodes linked by uniaxial elements (also named bars in the following) spatially arranged, and with masses concentrated at the nodes. These bars are organized in a cubic arrangement (**Figure 2(a)**) that is cubic cells with nine nodes as proposed by Nayfeh and Hefzy [47]. Each node has three degrees of freedom, corresponding to the nodal displacements in three orthogonal directions. The lengths of the normal and diagonal elements are $L_n=L$ and $L_d=(\sqrt{3}/2)L$, respectively, where L is the module length (**Figure 2(a)**).

Each uniaxial element is characterised by a constitutive law that relates internal force to the displacement [34], as is shown in **Figure 2(b)**, where F is the bar axial force and ε is the axial strain, being the area under such a curve (see triangle OAB in **Figure 2(b)**) linked to the dissipated energy per unit area of the bar cross-section. Under compression, the material behaves linearly. Thus, this nonlinear constitutive model allows to simulate both the bar damage (see the grey area in **Figure 2(b)**) and the bar failure when a critical strain condition is reached (that is, $\varepsilon=\varepsilon_u$ in **Figure 2(a)**). As can be seen in **Figure 2(b)**, the bilinear constitutive law also allows to capture the residual deformation (see the point O' in **Figure 2(b)**) due to the initial stiffness elements conservation.

Figure 2. LEDM: (a) Basic cubic module employed in the discretisation (normal bars in red and diagonal bars in black) and (b) bilinear constitutive law attributed to the bars.

Such a bilinear law, depends on three local parameters, that is:

- the bar specific stiffness, EA_i : it is a function of both the Young's modulus, E , and the cross-section area of the bar, A_i , where i is equal to n , for a normal bar, and equal to d , for a diagonal bar:

$$A_n = \frac{1}{2(1+\nu)} L_n^2 \quad (1)$$

$$A_d = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \delta A_n \quad (2)$$

where ν is the Poisson ratio of the material and δ is equal to $\delta = 9\nu/(4-8\nu)$.

It is important to note that for $\nu=0.25$, the equivalence with the isotropic continuum is complete; on the other hand, a difference arises in terms of shear, for $\nu \neq 0.25$, as detailed in Ref. [48];

- the ultimate strain, ε_u : it is the strain value for which the element loses its load-bearing capacity, that is the bar breaks. Such a parameter can be obtained from the following equation:

$$\int_0^{\varepsilon_u} F(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon = \frac{G_f A_i^*}{L_i} \quad (3)$$

where A_i^* is the equivalent fracture area of the i -th element, G_f is the fracture energy, and L_i is the bar length. Since the maximum dissipated energy per unit area is represented by the area of the region below the OAB triangle in **Figure 2(b)**, that is equal to $\varepsilon_u \varepsilon_p EA_i / 2$, the ultimate strain for the i -th bar, ε_u , is given by:

$$\varepsilon_u = \frac{G_f}{\varepsilon_p E} \left(\frac{A_i^*}{A_i} \right) \left(\frac{2}{L_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

The equivalent fracture area, A_i^* , is determined by equating the fracture energy calculated under continuum assumption with its discrete counterpart, that is $A_i^* = \left(\frac{3}{22} \right) L_i^2$. Details may be found in Refs **[35,39]**. It is worth noting that ε_u depends on both the material properties and the discretization level by means of L_i ;

- the critical strain, ε_p : it is the strain at the incipient damaging of the bar. Such a parameter is given by:

$$\varepsilon_p = \sqrt{\frac{G_f}{d_{eq} E}} \quad (5)$$

where d_{eq} is the equivalent length of the material. d_{eq} may be regarded as a material property, since it does not depend on the discretization level. Similar d_{eq} concepts have been discussed in the

literature, like the width of the plasticity region ahead the crack tip in the Dugdale model [49], or the Distances defined by Taylor in the context of the Theory of the Critical Distances (TCD) [50].

The equivalent length of the material, d_{eq} , can be computed by exploiting the concept of the stress brittleness number, s , proposed by Carpinteri [51] and given by:

$$s = \frac{K_c}{\sigma_p R_e^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

where σ_p is the tensile strength of the material and R_e is the structure characteristic size. It is important to highlight that s is able to represent the structural behaviour of the material, that is: for $s \rightarrow 0$ a brittle behaviour is expected, whereas when $s \rightarrow \infty$ a ductile behaviour is expected. Considering the relation between the critical stress intensity factor, K_c , and the fracture energy, G_f , (that is, $K_c = \sqrt{G_f E}$), and assuming a linear behaviour up to the incipient damaging of the bar (crack initiation), that is $\sigma_p = E \varepsilon_p$, Eq. (6) can be rewritten as:

$$d_{eq} = s^2 R_e \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the parameter ε_u may also be expressed as a function of d_{eq} , by combining Eq. (7) together with Eq. (4):

$$\varepsilon_u = \varepsilon_p d_{eq} \left(\frac{A_i^*}{A_i} \right) \left(\frac{2}{L_i} \right) \quad (8)$$

2.2 LDEM in the Ansys LS-DYNA environment

The LDEM is implemented into the Ansys LS-DYNA environment [44] (named LDEM-DYNA in the following) in order to develop a hybrid model, that is a LDE model combined with a FE model [52]. More precisely, the region of the structural component where the fracture is expected to occur is modelled by means of discrete elements, whereas the rest of the model is discretised by using finite elements. In Ref. [53] are highlighted the advantages of such a combination.

The bars, which composed the basic cubic module shown in **Figure 2(a)**, are modelled in LDEM-DYNA by using discrete spring elements, named Explicit Spring-Damper (COMBI165) [44]. The COMBI165 is able to generate a force that depends on the bar displacement. The mass in the LDEM-DYNA is concentrated in the COMBI165 nodes, by using the Explicit 3-D Structural Mass element (MASS166). The mass value depends on the node position within the basic module [52].

In the numerical simulation, possible imperfections present into the materials are taken into account through the statistical variation of one property of the material, represented by the fracture energy, assumed with a 3D Weibull statistical distribution. Details may be found in Refs. [52-54].

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN EXAMINED

The experimental campaign here examined [17,23,45,46] was performed on HDG specimens under constant bending moment, applied by using the

nonstandardised device shown in **Figure 3(a)** [55]. The specimens, manufactured from hot-rolled hyper-sandelin steel plates, had the geometrical configuration reported in **Figure 3(b)**, where the two holes were used to clamp the sample to the device. The force P and the bending angle, α_{exp} , were experimentally measured up to a maximum displacement of the crosshead equal to 35 mm.

The coating was performed by using two different baths:

- a pure zinc bath;
- a technological bath, obtained by employing a zinc bath with a tin addition (3% Sn in weight).

The galvanizing process is described in detail in Ref. [24].

Figure 3. Experimental campaign examined: (a) nonstandardised device employed to perform the bending tests [55] and (b) geometrical configuration of the specimen (sizes in mm).

The samples were submitted to five different dipping times, and more precisely: 15, 60, 180, 360 and 900s.

Using a Light Optical Microscopy (LOM), the average thickness of each intermetallic phase before testing was computed [24] and is here listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Average thickness of the intermetallic phases of the pure zinc bath and technological bath by varying the dipping time.

DIPPING TIME [s]	PHASE	PURE Zn B. [μm]	TECHN. B. [μm]
15	δ	13	15
	ζ	4	20
	η	9	22
60	δ	17	16
	ζ	10	20
	η	43	25
180	δ	11	13
	ζ	75	36
	η	16	27
360	δ	18	15
	ζ	140	52
	η	22	31
900	δ	12	34
	ζ	150	76
	η	28	47

4. LDEM-DYNA MODEL

The bending testing performed on the HDG specimens is here numerically simulated in the Ansys LS-DYNA environment. A bi-dimensional model is employed, due to the fact that the problem is characterized by a plane strain condition.

Two numerical models are developed, and more precisely:

- Model A, used to simulate the specimens galvanised by a pure zinc bath;
- Model B, used to simulate the specimens galvanised by a zinc bath with the addition of 3% by weight of tin.

4.1 Geometry, element types and boundary conditions

Each numerical model consists in the region of the specimen highlighted in **Figure 4(a)**, characterised by a length equal to $5t'$, being t' the overall thickness of the intermetallic phases.

Figure 4. Hybrid model: (a) schematisation of the HDG specimen, (b) element types employed and (c) boundary conditions.

The δ and ζ phases under tension (that is the intermetallic phases where a relevant crack pattern was experimentally observed [17,23,45,46]) are modelled by using discrete elements, whereas the steel and all the other intermetallic phases are modelled by using finite elements (**Figure 4(b)**). It is worth noting that the Γ phase is not included in the simulation, due to its infinitesimal layer thickness with respect to the other phases and negligible effect on the fracture analysis as reported in Ref. [12].

Figure 4(c) shows the boundary conditions applied to the hybrid model in order to have a constant bending moment in the model, that is the same loading condition characterising the specimen during the experimental campaign. In particular, along the x_2 axis, the nodal displacement in x_1 direction and the nodal rotation around x_3 direction are equal to zero, whereas along the axis parallel to x_2 , at a distance $5t'$ from x_2 , a linear prescribed displacement, $u_{x1}(t)$, characterised by a slope equal to α , is applied. The bending moment is calculated from the reaction forces registered along the x_2 axis, whereas the numerical bending angle, α_{num} (in degrees), is computed by using the following relationship:

$$\alpha_{num} = \left\{ \arctan \left[\frac{u_{x1,max}(t_{max})}{(h/2+t')} \right] \frac{l/2}{5t'} \right\} \frac{360^\circ}{2\pi} \quad (9)$$

where $u_{x_1, max}(t_{max})$ is the displacement along x_1 in correspondence of the top of the beam segment at the end of the numerical simulation, that is $t = t_{max}$.

4.2 Constitutive laws and materials/phases properties

Relatively to the part of hybrid model discretised by FEs, the elements employed are the explicit 3-D structural elements (SOLID164) in Ansys LS-DYNA environment [44]. The stress-strain curve for the steel, both under tension and compression, is typical of an elasto-plastic material with strain hardening (Figure 5(a)), whereas the stress-strain curve for the intermetallic phases, both under tension and compression, is typical of an elasto-perfectly plastic material (Figure 5(b)). The parameters characterising such stress-strain curves are listed in Table 3.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curves employed in the numerical model: (a) elasto-plastic with strain hardening and (b) elasto-perfectly plastic.

Table 3. Mechanical parameters of the steel, η phase and intermetallic phases under compression for both the Model A and B.

MATERIAL / PHASE	Ref.	E [GPa]	$\sigma_{y,H}$ [MPa]	$\sigma_{y,S}$ [MPa]	σ_{max} [MPa]	σ_r [MPa]	$\frac{\varepsilon_0}{10^{-3}}$	$\frac{\varepsilon_s}{10^{-3}}$	$\frac{\varepsilon_i}{10^{-2}}$	$\frac{\varepsilon_{max}}{10^{-2}}$	$\frac{\varepsilon_r}{10^{-1}}$
Steel	[24]	-	360	320	470	427	2.208	5.600	2.160	5.920	1.110
Inter. phases	[24]	75	210	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Relatively to the part of the hybrid model discretised by DEs both the mechanical properties of δ and ζ phases and the input parameters for the LDEM are listed in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of the δ and ζ phases under tension and LDEM input parameters for both the Model A and B.

		MECHANICAL PROPERTIES			LDEM INPUT	
MODEL	Ref.	E [GPa]	K_c [MPa \sqrt{m}]	σ_p [MPa]	d_{eq} [m]	G_f [Nm]
MODEL A						
δ phase	[12,24]	140	2.0	450	$1.98(10)^{-5}$	28.57
ζ phase	[12,24]	107	4.0	210	$3.63(10)^{-4}$	149.53
MODEL B						
δ phase	[-]	140	6.0	450	$1.78(10)^{-4}$	257.14
ζ phase	[-]	107	12.0	210	$7.11(10)^{-4}$	1345.79

More precisely, the mechanical properties in terms of elastic modulus, E , fracture toughness, K_c , and tensile stress at incipient damaging of the bar, $\sigma_p = F_p / A_i^*$, for the δ and ζ phases in a pure zinc bath (Model A) are taken from the literature [12,24]. For the technological bath (Model B), is assumed a value for E and σ_p equal to those of the Model A, whereas K_c is assumed to be three times the value of that used in Model A. Such an assumption is justified by the fact that during the experimental campaign a more ductile

behaviour was observed for this type of bath with respect to the pure zinc bath.

4.3 Fracture energy random field

Relatively to the \mathbf{G}_f random field, the correlation lengths equal to $l_{cx}=10L$ and $l_{cy}=3L$ are assumed. The coefficient of variation of the fracture energy, CV , is taken equal to 100% for the bars, whereas that related to the cubic module is equal to about 40%. More details about the random field can be found in Ref. [54].

4.4 Discretisation

The No. of elements used, together with the module length, L , for the DEs, are listed in **Table 5** for the Model A and in **Table 6** for the Model B.

Perfect adhesion is assumed between each layer.

Table 5. Model A: No. of FEs, and No. of DEs, together with the module length, L , employed for each dipping time examined.

MODEL A	Dip. time [s]	FEs No.	DEs No.	L [μm]
Steel	15	6500	-	-
	60	8750	-	-
	180	6500	-	-
	360	7400	-	-
	900	7900	-	-
Inter. phases	15	520	-	-
	60	700	-	-
	180	520	-	-
	360	592	-	-
	900	632	-	-
δ phase	15	-	1690	1.00
	60	-	1575	2.00
	180	-	390	4.00
	360	-	444	6.00

	900	-	316	6.00
ζ phase	15	-	520	1.00
	60	-	875	2.00
	180	-	2470	4.00
	360	-	3404	6.00
	900	-	3950	6.00

Table 6. Model B: No. of FEs, and No. of DEs, together with the module length, L , employed for each dipping time examined.

MODEL B	Dip. time [s]	FEs No.	DEs No.	L [μm]
Steel	15	7150	-	-
	60	7650	-	-
	180	7450	-	-
	360	8100	-	-
	900	8850	-	-
Inter. phases	15	572	-	-
	60	612	-	-
	180	596	-	-
	360	648	-	-
	900	708	-	-
δ phase	15	-	1144	2.00
	60	-	1224	2.00
	180	-	745	2.50
	360	-	810	6.00
	900	-	1416	6.00
ζ phase	15	-	1430	2.00
	60	-	1530	2.00
	180	-	2086	2.50
	360	-	2754	6.00
	900	-	3009	6.00

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Model A

In **Figure 6**, the results obtained by using the Model A, in terms of bending moment against the half bending angle, are reported for a pure zinc bath characterised by a dipping time equal to 15s, and then compared with both the experimental results and the numerical ones obtained by using the FE model reported in Ref. **[24]**. More

precisely, the numerical results are here obtained by employing four different random fields for the energy release rate, \mathbf{G}_f (see No. 1 to No. 4 curves in **Figure 6**). Note that, in such a Figure, the dashed lines define an error, with respect to the experimental bending, moment equal to $\pm 10\%$.

Figure 6. Bending moment vs. half bending angle for the case of a pure zinc bath (Model A) characterised by a dipping time of 15s: experimental data, numerical results obtained by the FE model reported in Ref. [24], and numerical results here obtained by employing four different \mathbf{G}_f random fields.

It can be observed that the different \mathbf{G}_f random fields implemented into the hybrid model do not affect the global behaviour of the model. Moreover, it can be noted that:

- in the elastic regime, that is up to a value of the half bending angle equal to 4° , the numerical bending moment overestimates the

experimental one that is, the slope of the elastic branch numerically obtained is greater with respect to the experimental one;

- in the plastic regime, that is for values of the half bending angle from about 4° to about 34° , the numerical bending moment does not differ more than $\pm 10\%$ with respect to the corresponding experimental one;
- in the unloading phase, the numerical model does not capture the slope of the unloading branch being such a slope assumed to be equal to that of the elastic loading branch;
- for each dipping time examined, the numerical results are in agreement with the numerical ones reported in Ref. [24].

Figure 7 shows the comparison between the crack patterns at the end of the simulations, obtained by the hybrid numerical model by varying G_f (see **Figure 7(a)**), and the metallography of the tensile side of the sample obtained after testing (see **Figure 7(b)**), for a dipping time equal to 15s.

Figure 7. Crack patterns in the case of a pure zinc bath (Model A) at a dipping time of 15s: (a) numerical results here obtained by using four different fracture energy random fields, at the end of the simulations, and (b) metallography of the tensile side of the HDG specimen, at the end of the testing.

In **Figure 7(a)**, the broken bars are coloured in red, the damaged bars in orange and the undamaged bars in cyan.

From the metallography reported in **Figure 7(b)**, an average distance between the radial cracks equal to about $40 \mu\text{m}$ is measured, whereas in the numerical simulations such a distance, measured along the dashed line in **Figure 7(a)**, is equal to about $80 \mu\text{m}$. More

precisely, for the simulation No.3 the average distance between the cracks is equal to about 40 μm .

Moreover, although the metallographic analysis seems to indicate only the presence of Mode I radial cracks, in the numerical simulations there is a predominance of Mode I cracks, but also Mixed Mode (I+II) cracks are found. Generally, the crack orientation changing is observed between the δ and ζ phases (see the dashed line in **Figure 7(a)**).

In **Figure 8**, the results obtained by using the Model A, in terms of bending moment against the half bending angle, are reported for pure zinc baths characterised by dipping times equal to 60s, 180s, 360s and 900s, and then compared with both the experimental and FEM results [24]. Since it has been proved that the random field does not influence the global bending behaviour of the model, only one simulation is performed for each case.

Figure 8. Bending moment vs. half bending angle in the case of pure zinc baths characterised by dipping times of: (a) 60s, (b) 180s, (c) 360s and (d) 900s. Experimental data, numerical results obtained by the FE model reported in Ref. [24], and numerical results obtained by the hybrid Model A are reported.

The observations that can be made on **Figure 8** are similar to those performed on **Figure 7**.

The crack patterns at the end of the simulations, obtained by the hybrid Model A for the dipping times equal to 60s, 180s, 360s and 900s, are compared with the corresponding metallographies in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9. Numerical simulations (left-hand side) and metallographies (right-hand side) in the case of pure zinc baths (Model A) characterised by dipping times of: (a) 60s, (b) 180s, (c) 360s and (d) 900s.

For the dipping times equal to 60s and 180s (**Figure 9(a)** and **Figure 9(b)**), it can be observed that Mode I cracks are predominant in both cases. Kinked cracks are observed for the numerical simulations corresponding to the dipping times equal to 360s and 900s (**Figure 9(c)** and **Figure 9(d)**). Kinked cracks can be also noted in the metallographies. Moreover, for such dipping times, longitudinal cracks are also observed at both the δ - ζ interface and the steel- δ interface, as highlighted by the blue arrows.

To evaluate the damage evolution, the crack patterns at different half bending angle values are reported in **Figure 10** for each dipping time examined. More precisely, half bending angles of 1° , 2° , 4° , 8° , 18° , 26° and 34° are selected. For the dipping time equal to 15s, the simulation No. 1 of **Figure 7(a)** is chosen to be analysed.

Figure 10. Damage evolution numerically obtained by the Model A at different half bending angle values, for different dipping times: (a) 15s, (b) 60s, (c) 180s, (d) 360, and (e) 900s.

In **Figure 10(a)**, it can be observed, as previously mentioned, that the damage starts at the δ - ζ interface. For angles greater

than 2° , the damage is spread across both the δ and the ζ phases. The number of damaged bars at the end of the simulation, that is at 34° (reported in an orange colour in the Figure) is higher than the other dipping times (**Figure 10(b)-(e)**). Mode I and Mixed Mode cracks are observed.

In **Figure 10(b)** the damage starts at the ζ - η interface. Mode I cracks propagate for a half bending angle greater than 2° .

In **Figure 10(c)** the damage starts at the steel- δ interface. At the end of the elastic branch, that is at a half bending angle equal to 4° , macro cracks under Mode I are observed. For half bending angles greater than 18° , longitudinal cracks develop in the samples at the steel- δ interface.

In **Figure 10(d)** and **Figure 10(e)** at a half bending angles equal to 1° the damage is present in both δ and ζ phases. Kinked cracks are developed at the end of the elastic region, that is at a half bending angle equal to 4° . For half bending angles greater than 18° , longitudinal cracks develop in the samples both in δ - ζ interface and steel- δ interface.

According to the experimental results reported in Refs. **[17,23,45,46]** the better galvanizing condition has been obtained for a dipping time equal to 60s due to the fact that the damage, measured as the radial crack density (cracks No./length), is lower with respect to that corresponding to the other dipping times examined, that is, the intermetallic phases present a more ductile behaviour.

In order to verify if the above conclusion can be obtained also from the numerical simulations, the stress brittleness number, s , is considered (see Eq.(6)). As a matter of fact, as pointed out by Birck et al. [56], that analysed the values of s to classify the behaviour of structures modelled by using the LDEM, for values of s :

- lower than 2, a brittle structural behaviour is expected;
- greater than 2, a ductile behaviour is attained.

For the δ and ζ intermetallic phases, the s parameter is computed for the different dipping times examined by means of Eq.(6), exploiting the mechanical properties reported in **Table 6**, and assuming as the structure characteristic size, R_e , the average thickness of the intermetallic phases reported in **Table 2**. For such phases, the s parameter against the dipping time is reported in **Figure 11**.

Figure 11. Stress brittleness number versus dipping time for the δ and ζ phases in the case of a pure zinc bath (Model A).

According to the statement reported in Ref.[56], it can be observed that the δ phase is characterized by a brittle behaviour. For such a phase, s can be considered as a constant and equal to about 1.7. On the other hand, the ζ phase presents a ductile behaviour for dipping times equal to 15s, 60s and 180s, whereas for the dipping times of 360s and 900s a brittle behaviour is expected. More precisely, at 900s the brittleness of the δ and ζ phases is quite similar.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the better galvanizing condition is obtained for a dipping time equal to 60s, in accordance with the experimental evidence. As a matter of fact, by considering the more ductile intermetallic phase between the phases δ and ζ , although the value of s is greater for a dipping time equal to 15s (that is, 9.5 versus 6.0), the crack pattern numerically obtained for a dipping time of 60s is less severe with respect to that related to 15s, being the radial crack density greater for a dipping time of 15s (0.0150 from **Figure (7)** against 0.0067 from **Figure 9(a)**).

5.2 Model B

In **Figure 12**, the results obtained by using the Model B, in terms of bending moment against the half bending angle, are reported for technological bath characterised by dipping times equal to 15s, 60s, 180s, 360s and 900s, and then compared with both the

experimental results and the numerical results obtained by using the FE model reported in Ref. [24]. Since it has been proved for Model A (see Section 5.1) that the random field does not influence the global bending behaviour of the model, only one simulation is performed for each case.

Figure 12. Numerical bending moment vs. half bending angle in the case of technological bath characterised by dipping times of: (a) 15s, (b) 60s, (c) 180s, (d) 360s and (e) 900s. The experimental data and the numerical results obtained by the FE model reported in Ref. **[24]** are also reported.

It can be observed that:

- for the dipping time equal to 60s, in the elastic regime (that is up to a value of the half bending angle equal to about 4°) the slope of the elastic branch numerically obtained agrees with the experimental one, being the numerical curve within a scatter of $\pm 10\%$ with respect to the experimental one;
- for the dipping times equal to 15s, 180s, 360s and 900s, in the elastic regime the slope of the elastic branch numerically obtained is greater with respect to the experimental one;
- for each dipping time examined, in the plastic regime (that is for values of the half bending angle from about 4° to about 34°) the numerical bending moment does not differ more than $\pm 10\%$ with respect to the corresponding experimental one;
- for each dipping time examined, in the unloading phase, the numerical model does not capture the slope of the unloading branch being such a slope assumed to be equal to that of the elastic loading branch;
- for each dipping time examined, the numerical results are in agreement with the experimental ones reported in Ref. **[24]**.

The crack patterns at the end of the simulations, obtained by the hybrid Model B for the dipping times equal to 15s, 60s, 180s,

360s and 900s, are compared with the corresponding metallographies in **Figure 13**.

Figure 13. Numerical simulations (left-hand side) and metallographies (right-hand side) in the case of technological baths (Model B) characterised by dipping times of: (a) 15s, (b) 60s, (c) 180s, (d) 360s and (e) 900s.

It can be observed that for such a bath type, the number of cracks is lower with respect to the pure zinc bath, in accordance with the experimental evidence. Kinked cracks are observed in both the numerical simulations and the metallographies. For the dipping times equal to 60s and 360s (**Figure 13(b)** and **Figure 13(d)**), the crack orientation changing is observed between the δ - ζ interface.

Moreover, for the dipping times equal to 15s, 360s and 900s (**Figure 13(a)**, **Figure 13(d)** and **Figure 13(e)**), longitudinal cracks close to the steel- δ interface are observed in both the numerical simulations and the metallographies.

To evaluate the damage evolution, the crack patterns at different half bending angle values are reported in **Figure 14** for each dipping time examined. More precisely, half bending angles of 1° , 2° , 4° , 8° , 18° , 26° and 34° are selected.

Figure 14. Damage evolution numerically obtained by the Model B at different half bending angle values, for different dipping times: (a) 15s, (b) 60s, (c) 180s, (d) 360, and (e) 900s.

In **Figures 14(a), (b) and (e)** it can be observed that for small half bending angles (that is, 1° and 2°), the damage is distributed

in both the δ and ζ phases, whereas in **Figures 14(c) and (d)** the damage starts in the ζ phase.

In **Figure 14(a)** small cracks appear in both the δ and ζ phases for a half bending angle equal to 8° . The coalescence of such small cracks into kinked macro cracks is observed for half bending angles greater than 18° .

In **Figure 14(b)** Mixed Mode cracks are observed. The crack orientation changes in correspondence of the δ - ζ interface.

In **Figure 14(c)** a small crack appears in the ζ phase for a half bending angle equal to 4° , that is at the end of the elastic branch. For higher values of the half bending angle, only one kinked crack is observed through both the δ and ζ phases.

In **Figure 14(d)** a mixed mode crack propagation is observed for half bending angles greater than 8° . Moreover, longitudinal cracks appear both at the δ - ζ interface (at a half bending angle equal to 8°) and at the steel- δ interface (at a half bending angle equal to 18°).

In **Figure 14(e)** a small crack appears in the ζ phase for a half bending angle equal to 4° , that is at the end of the elastic branch. For half bending angles greater than 18° , both Mixed Mode cracks and longitudinal cracks at the steel- δ interface can be observed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the global bending behaviour of HDG hot-rolled hyper-sandelin plates has been numerically simulated by using a hybrid FE-LDE model developed by employing Ansys LS-DYNA finite element code in conjunction with the LDEM. Two coating types have been considered and more precisely: a pure zinc coating and a zinc-based coating with 3% Sn addition by weight. The global bending behaviour has been compared with both experimental data and other FE numerical results, previously obtained by some of the present authors. Moreover, the crack patterns numerically obtained have been compared with the experimental observations (obtained by means of a LOM) of the longitudinal section of the plates at the end of testing.

The main conclusions that can be highlighted are as follows:

- in the elastic regime, the numerical bending moment generally overestimates the corresponding experimental one;
- in the plastic regime, the numerical bending moment does not differ more than $\pm 10\%$ from the corresponding experimental one;
- the proposed hybrid models have demonstrated to be able to simulate the phenomena involved during fracture process, and more precisely: damage initiation, crack propagation mode, crack bifurcation and longitudinal crack propagation, showing a good agreement with the metallographies obtained by LOM.

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